

Thermal behavior and photoluminescence properties of Er and Nd doped $Y_2O_3-Al_2O_3$ glasses

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ABSTRACT

Yttrium aluminate glasses (76.8 mol.% of Al_2O_3 , 23.2 mol. % of Y_2O_3) doped with Er^{3+} and Nd^{3+} ions at different concentration level (0.25 mol.%, 0.5 mol.% and 0.75 mol.%) were prepared by flame synthesis in the form of glass microspheres. The prepared samples were characterized by SEM (**Fig.1**) and XRD analysis. For study of thermal behavior of prepared systems, DSC analysis in temperature interval 35-1200°C, with heating rate 10°C/min was performed in nitrogen atmosphere. The list of prepared samples and basic properties are shown in (**Tab. 1**). The two exothermic effects (≈ 940 , $\approx 1010^\circ C$) which can be assigned to crystallization of YAG phase in two steps were observed in DSC records of all prepared samples. The high temperature XRD measurements were performed in temperature interval 600-1200°C, with heating rate 5°C/min for more detailed study of thermal behavior of prepared systems and for study of temperature dependence of YAG content in samples during thermal treatment. In the whole temperature interval only YAG phase crystallization was observed. Based on excitation spectra of Er- and Nd- doped samples measured in the interval 250-750 nm, appropriate excitation wavelengths (380 nm for Er- and 360 nm for Nd- doped samples) were selected. The emission spectra were measured in VIS and NIR region in case of Er doped samples and in NIR region in case of Nd doped samples. All measured emission spectra (PL) (**Fig.2**) consist of characteristic bands due to the typical 4f-4f transitions in Er and Nd ions. From comparison of measured intensities it is evident, that the highest intensities were obtained for 0.5 mol. % Er doped sample (in both, NIR and VIS spectral regions). In the case of Nd doped samples, the maximum intensity value was found for the sample doped with 0.75 mol.% of Nd. The isothermal crystallization experiments at 1000°C and 1500°C were also performed with the dwell time of 20, 40 and 60 min. Measured emission spectra of crystallized samples shown slow increase of intensities in samples after 20 min annealing at 1000°C and Stark splitting of emission bands in samples after 40 and 60 min annealing at 1000°C and after 20, 40 and 60 min annealing at 1500°C, whereas further increase of splitted emission bands intensities was not observed.

From comparison of emission spectra of samples annealed at 1000°C for 40 and 60 min and emission spectra of samples annealed at 1500°C for 20, 40 and 60 min can be assumed, that the crystallisation of $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ has no significant influence on the PL properties of crystallised microspheres[1].

Tab.1: The list of the samples and their basic characteristics

sample	Al_2O_3 [mol.%]	Y_2O_3 [mol.%]	Er_2O_3 [mol.%]	Nd_2O_3 [mol.%]	T_{p1} [°C]	T_{p2} [°C]	XRD
A6Y4Nd0.25	76.8	22.95	0.00	0.25	941	1010	amorphous
A6Y4Nd0.50	76.8	22.70	0.00	0.50	941	1011	amorphous
A6Y4Nd0.75	76.8	22.45	0.00	0.75	940	1012	amorphous
A6Y4Er0.25	76.8	22.95	0.25	0.00	941	1008	amorphous
A6Y4Er0.50	76.8	22.70	0.50	0.00	941	1008	amorphous
A6Y4Er0.75	76.8	22.45	0.75	0.00	941	1012	amorphous

Fig.1 SEM micrograph of AYE-Er0.5 prepared microspheres. The hollow microspheres are marked by arrows.

Fig.2 The comparison of luminescence spectra measured in VIS spectral region of glass. AYE-Er0.5 and glass AYE-Er0.5 crystallized at 1000°C and 1500°C for 60 min (a) and in NIR region (b). The comparison of luminescence spectra measured in NIR region of glass AYE-Nd0.75 and glass AYE-Nd0.75 crystallized at 1000°C and 1500°C for 60 min (c).

References

[1] A. Prnová, J. Valúchová, N. Mutlu, M. Parchoviansky, R. Klement, A. Plško, D. Galusek, Thermal behaviour and photoluminescence properties of Er and Nd doped yttrium aluminate glasses, *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, submitted.

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